

FACTORS AND STRATEGIES AFFECTING VOTING BEHAVIOR OF REGISTERED VOTERS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF SILANG, CAVITE

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ABSTRACT

In Article V, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution, it is specified that suffrage is a right granted to all citizens of the Philippines who are not disqualified by law. Suffrage entails the privilege to participate in public elections, whether local or national, by voting and being a candidate under certain conditions. The election of public officials in the Philippines is considered a significant event, drawing voters' attention to sociocultural issues, which are integral to the democratic process. Elections are commonly viewed as the embodiment of public will and the exercise of the people's sovereign authority in modern democratic societies. Understanding the factors and strategies influencing voting behavior in elections is crucial to comprehending the dynamics of selecting political candidates and the impact of voter choices on them. This study delves into the factors and strategies that influence the voting behavior of registered voters in Silang, Cavite. It aims to address various inquiries posed to respondents, such as determining their demographic characteristics, identifying factors influencing their voting behavior, analyzing election campaign strategies employed by political candidates to sway voter decisions, and exploring potential relationships between factors, campaign strategies, and voting behavior. Furthermore, the study examines how factors like educational background, family ties, political party allegiance, and candidate platforms, in conjunction with strategies such as campaign advertisements, social media promotions, and the distribution of promotional items, impact voter preferences.

Keywords: *election, platforms, political party affiliation, family affiliation, campaign strategies*

INTRODUCTION

"The power lies in the power of the votes of those whom the masses have vested their power by giving their vote." — Amit Abraham

"Man is by nature a political animal." One of the great ideas of the great philosopher Aristotle. In its broadest sense, politics is the activity of the people in making, preserving, and amending the general rules under which they live. Knowing the view of politics is evident in our everyday lives. It does not only talk about 'what concerns the state?' but also specifically, "What are our concerns?"

Now, the word politics comes from the Greek word polis, meaning everything that concerns or belongs to the polis, or city-state. However, in the scientific journal of Modebadze (2010), he states that the definition of politics varies from time to time and from place to place. In other words, politics is a loaded term. It has a wide range of meanings when used in everyday life. Politics is defined in such different ways as the study of conflict resolution, the art of government, the conduct and management of public affairs, and so on. Hence, the given definition by Modebadze (2010) proved that politics takes place in all aspects of human life. Also, in understanding politics, it will always include the involvement of human needs and desires and how such decisions are made without being limited by the voters in every election. It may also include the study of how such decisions should be made. Politics will not be separated from the government.

In the Philippine political context, on January 17, 1973, the late President Ferdinand E. Marcos proclaimed the new Constitution and a new form of government. The new Constitution, which is the 1973 Philippine Constitution, took effect and was adopted after its ratification, amidst widespread controversy and protest. With the proclamation of the new Constitution, the presidential form of government was changed to a modified parliamentary form of government. Wherein President Marcos will be the Chief Executive and Prime Minister of the Philippines. Furthermore, Marcos abolished Congress and was replaced by an elected unicameral National Assembly, known as Batasang Pambansa, in which he also has legislative power. Also on February 22–25, 1986, during the reign of the late dictator President Marcos, the EDSA Revolution happened. The Filipino people came to EDSA to protest and overthrow Marcos as President of the Philippines. The late President Corazon Aquino was the one who advocated and fought to bring back democracy to the Philippines. Then a revolutionary government was formed. After a long reign as dictator, Marcos was overthrown, and Corazon Aquino was proclaimed the new President of the Philippines through an election. The Constitutional Commission drafted a new charter and ratified it in February 1987. The 1987 Philippine Constitution brings back the rebirth of the old bicameral system and the unitary, democratic, presidential, and republican states. This history made the Philippine election important and powerful because it prevented the politician from ruling for a long period by having a term limit.

In exploration, under the 1987 Philippine Constitution, all elective officials, particularly the President, Vice President, Senators, Members of the House of

Representatives, Local Chief Executives, and Local Legislators, are chosen by a direct vote of the people, the registered voters, through a first-past-the-post system. In Article V, Section 1 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution stated that "suffrage may be exercised by all citizens of the Philippines not otherwise disqualified by law, who are at least eighteen years of age, and who shall have resided in the Philippines for at least one year, and in the place wherein they propose to vote, for at least six months immediately preceding the election. No literacy, property, or other substantive requirements shall be imposed on the exercise of suffrage." With regards to that constitutional provision, suffrage is the right to vote in public elections about local and national elections in the Philippines.

Electing any public officers in their respective positions through election is the most exciting event in the Philippines. Voters are diehard supporters of the candidates they support. Also, the political candidates conduct many political campaigns and use propaganda to persuade the voters to vote for them. Elections in the Philippines are personality-driven, and the right of suffrage is considered a vital exercise of democracy, as provided in our constitution (Velmonte, 2020). It can be concluded that elections are always the most highly anticipated events in the Philippines. Citizen participation in elections enhances their love for the nation.

Furthermore, political campaigns, or election campaigns, are how candidates and political parties prepare and present their ideas and positions on issues to the voters in the period preceding Election Day. Contestants used a variety of techniques to reach voters and deliver their messages, including traditional and new media, public events, written materials, or other means. Through this election campaign, registered voters have the right to choose which candidates they will vote for. The campaign is a big part of the election because in this part, candidates use various media to promote and market a political party or candidate for the electorate to support and vote for. Through different political strategies to campaign for every candidate for a specific position, politicians used various means to promote and advertise themselves to the people.

According to Assay (2020), in his insight into the book entitled "Political Propaganda, Advertising, and Public Relations," the main actors in the campaign and election are the political parties and aspirants. In each election, the role of electoral campaigns in modern democratic politics cannot be overstated. In every state, elected officials are expected to adopt policies that are consistent with voters' preferences. However, Assay mentioned four (4) important election campaigns in every election. First, it is the time to discuss the different political parties affiliated with every political candidate; second, the political candidates have time to address their agendas through election meetings attended by the voters; third, in every story in the community and any news publication, elected-related information is discussed; and lastly, this is also the time by which the voters become aware of the political propaganda and agendas of each political candidate and political parties affiliated with them. For political candidates to succeed in their political ambitions, a political campaign is very important. Posit that an effective campaign requires enough resources, strong political parties, and strategies to gain the trust of the voters.

On the other hand, the research of Andrews (2002) at Eastern Illinois University, Illinois, the United States, entitled "The Effect of Electoral Systems on Voting Behavior and Party Development: The Case of Canada" provides that there are approaches and methods that are used to analyze the relationship between voting, parties, and the electoral system. Both behavioral and institutional approaches are used to analyze voter turnout. Also, the author, beyond his study, focused on the impact that the timing of elections has on government formation and the interconnectedness between these areas as they relate to party development and voting behavior. The result and discussion of Andrew's research stated that there are a substantial number of variables that contribute to determining voter turnout. The development always correlated to voting behavior in the majority of areas in Canada.

In the context of the voting behavior of Edlin, Gelman, and Kaplan (2007), the proponents of the rational model suggest that people vote by assessing the pros and cons of each candidate or political party, including their promises. They argue that *"voters decide whether to vote and how to vote, based on maximizing an expected utility with both selfish and social terms."* They attribute that agents in rational-choice models are typically assumed to have 'selfish' preferences. It is important to explain that it is rational for people to vote. We vote not for direct individual gain but to perceive it as the common good. This model explains not just why voters vote but also how rational people vote. This voting theory explains how individuals, particularly voters, should work with social rather than selfish utility functions.

Additionally, elections were used in ancient Athens, Rome, and the selection of popes and Holy Roman emperors. The origins of elections in the contemporary world lie in the gradual emergence of representative governments in Europe and North America beginning in the 17th century. Besides, it is the way to have a concept of representation. Moreover, an election is defined as the formal process of selecting a person for public office or of accepting or rejecting a political proposition by voting. In a democracy, the right to vote is vested in the people with certain requirements. (Webb et al., 2020)

In this study, which was conducted from September 2021 to June 2022, the authors asserted and understood the given factors and strategies that affect the voting behavior of the registered voters in the Municipality of Silang, Cavite. Specifically, it aimed to: (1) determine the demographic profile of the participants; (2) identify the following factors affecting the voting behavior of the participants; (3) identify the election campaign strategies used by a political candidate to affect the voting behavior of the participants; (4) determine if there is a significant relationship between factors and voting behavior; and (5) determine if there is a significant relationship between strategies and voting behavior. It showed better ideas on how people and others affect their voting behaviors through given factors and strategies. Every voter response in an election has a significant impact on the strategies of political campaigns. It says that an election is a formal process of selecting a person for public office or accepting or rejecting a political proposition by voting. More specifically, the Philippines 2022 national and local elections are mentioned here, particularly the upcoming local election in Silang, Cavite.

In the theoretical framework, the idea of the early Swedish economist Knut Wicksell's Modern Public Choice Theory (1896) is emphasized. It helped to provide a background on motions of voters' behavior in every election and explains how political campaigns and strategies act as a factor in making the voter's results from its outcome to the development of a particular society. It dealt with the use of tools to solve traditional problems in political science. It worked in the aspects of political behavior that often influence the voter's behavior when choosing public officials. According to him, there were three tenets to this theory. First, the use of the individual as the common decision unit there is no rational decision made by an aggregate whole, but rather a decision made by the combined choices of the individuals. Second, true economics pertains to the use of markets in the political system. Lastly, the nature of individual interest in the political system is highly needed to address the concern of choosing public officials in every election.

In continuation of Wicksell's theory, James Buchanan calls Knut Wicksell his intellectual father and adopts the Wicksellian tradition in his study year of 1946. He supported the idea of an early precursor to that theory. He applies theories and methods to analyze political behavior. Wicksell and Buchanan's idea presumes that participants in the political sphere aspire to promote the common good. Consider Shughart II's (2019) analysis of the idea of Wicksell and Buchanan that by choosing public servants, we carry out the will of the people. In connection with Wicksell's idea, most theories of elections assume that voters and political actors are fully rational. While these formulations produce many insights, they also generate anomalies, most famously about turnout. The rise of behavioral economics has posed new challenges to the premise of rationality. A behavioral theory of elections is based on the notion that all actors, including politicians as well as voters, are only rational. The theory posits learning via trial and error: actions that surpass an actor's aspiration level are more likely to be used in the future, while those that fall short are less likely to be tried later. Based on this idea of adaptation, the authors construct formal models of party competition, turnout, and voters' choices of candidates. These models predict substantial turnout levels, voters sorting into parties, and winning parties adopting centrist platforms. In multiparty elections, voters can coordinate vote choices on majority-preferred candidates while all candidates garner significant vote shares. Overall, the behavioral theory and its models produce macro implications consistent with the data on elections, and they use plausible micro assumptions about the cognitive capacities of politicians and voters. A computational model accompanies the book and can be used as a tool for further research (Bendor et al., 2011). The behavioral theory is closely connected to the public choice theory since they both assume that in political areas, individual choice largely reflects the political system. In this situation, the researchers believed that it is important to understand individual opinions, preferences, interests, and behaviors in decision-making. It displaced presumptions that we used to analyze political candidates' actions and behavior before making any decisions, primarily on voting and choosing political candidates. The aforementioned theory will guide the entire study on understanding voters' choices in selecting political candidates in each election in relation to their political campaigns and propaganda.

Lastly, this study is designed to know what factors and strategies affect the behavior of the registered voters in the Municipality of Silang, Cavite. Since this municipality is first-class and one of the most populated and biggest land areas in the province of Cavite, the author focused most of their attention on the local government election. As of November 12, 2021, Silang, Cavite, has a total of 144,088 registered Filipino voters based on the Statistical Report by Age Bracket released by the Commission on Elections, Silang, Cavite. In the age bracket of 30–54 years old, there are 74,780 registered voters. For the 2022 local elections, the author chose to determine the factors and strategies that affect the voting behavior of the registered voters in Silang, Cavite.

Research Questions

1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of the following categories:
 - a. age;
 - b. years of residency; and
 - c. years in being registered voter in Silang, Cavite?
2. What are factors affecting the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:
 - a. educational background;
 - b. family affiliation;
 - c. political party or affiliation; and
 - d. platforms?
3. What are the election campaign strategies used by a political candidate to affect the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:
 - a. campaign jingle;
 - b. social media advertisement; and
 - c. merchandise (ex. jacket, cap, bracelet, fan, etc.)?
4. Is there significant relationships between factors and voting behavior?
5. Is there significant relationships between election campaign strategies and voting behavior?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design, specifically correlational research. This method is used to obtain a clearer understanding of the quantitative data and then to provide a better explanation of the study through the different sources of information mentioned in this chapter. The method aimed to give a voice to study participants and ensure that the study findings were grounded in participants' experiences. On another point, the effectiveness of quantitative method design (correlational research) for this study is heavily based on the skills, knowledge, efforts, and abilities of the author, while the outcomes may be perceived as reliable because they mostly come from reliable sources of data, primarily the responses of the participants. In

general, it is intended to correlate the significant relationships between factors, election campaign strategies, and voting behavior. This method design gave authors across research disciplines various approaches to answering the research questions of the study. In the data, the research design needs to be clear to the reader of your study.

The author used the Purposive Sampling Technique and the Snowball Sampling Technique for the quantitative analysis. Authors often believe that they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, which will result in saving time and money. It is also selecting a sample "on the basis of your own knowledge of the population, its elements, and the nature of your research aims," and then the elements are randomly selected from each of these. Whereas the participants will be chosen in line with the specific qualities, namely, that they shall not be first-time voters and have lived for at least ten years in the Municipality of Silang, Cavite. On the other hand, it gathered samples for the study using snowball sampling, which is when research participants recruit other participants for a test or study. It is used when potential participants are hard to find. It's called "snowball sampling" because (in theory), once you have the ball rolling, it picks up more "snow" along the way and becomes larger and larger. It means that it is a recruitment technique in which research participants are asked to assist the researcher in identifying other potential subjects. Therefore, the participants will be asked if they can refer possible participants to the researcher who fit the standards or requirements set by the author to gain more participants in their study.

The participants of the study were the 448 registered voters, ranging in age from 30 to 54 years old, with at least 10 years of residency and 10 years of being a voter in Silang, Cavite. The above coming from sixty four (64) Barangays namely: Acacia, Atlas, Anahaw 1, Anahaw 2, Balite 1, Balite 2, Balubad, Banaba, Batas, Biga 1, Biga 2, Biluso, Bucal, Buho, Bulihan, Cabangaan, Carmen, Hoyo, Hukay, Iba, Inchican, Ipil 1, Ipil 2, Kalubkob, Kaong, Lalaan I, Lalaan II, Litlit, Lucsuhin, Lumil, Maguyam, Malabag, Malaking Tatiao, Mataas Na Burol, Munting Ilog, Narra 1, Narra 2, Narra 3, Paligawan, Pasong Langka, Poblacion Barangay 1, Poblacion Barangay 2, Poblacion Barangay 3, Poblacion Barangay 4, Poblacion Barangay 5, Poooc 1, Poooc 2, Pulong Bunga, Pulong Saging, Puting Kahoy, Sabutan, San Miguel 1, San Miguel 2, San Vicente 1, San Vicente 2, Santol, Tartaria, Tibig, Toledo, Tubuan 1, Tubuan 2, Tubuan 3, Ulat, and Yakal.

The author estimated from the sample frame of existing data that the population of registered voters in Silang aged 30-54 is 74,780. Using Slovin's formula, the researchers will have a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. For the survey questionnaires, the participants were 398 registered voters from Silang, Cavite; the researchers came up with this number by using Slovin's Method. From this, the researchers decided to round this number up to 448 and divide it by 64 barangays, yielding a total of 7 participants per barangay in Silang, Cavite.

The author desired to obtain information from books, online articles and journals, theses and research studies, and some other resources that supported the research study. Also, it used a self-made questionnaire that included different questions related to the topic of the study. Moreover, the survey questionnaire was distributed to the

participants with an age range of 30–54 years old, at least 10 years of residency, and 10 years of being a voter in Silang, Cavite. Furthermore, the author began this study by sending a request letter to the Commission on Elections in Silang, Cavite, for the updated total registered voters in their city. The purpose of the study, mode of administration of the research instrument, and other information about the study were explained in the letter.

Also, this study used a self-made questionnaire via a Google Form and a printed copy to test its validity and reliability. The self-made questionnaire was validated by the expert during the study, and the content validity and reliability were validated and certified by the statistician.

The research instrument was composed of three (3) parts:

The first part (Part I) of the questionnaire was intended to elicit basic information, which identifies the demographic profile of participants from Silang, Cavite, with the considered preferences in terms of age, years of residency, and years of being registered voters.

The second part (Part II) of the questionnaire contained a statement on a scale of 1–5, designed to be answered and elicit responses from the participants. It finds out that the extent to which this affects their voting behavior by influencing voters' selection of political candidates in every election depends on several election campaign strategies mentioned in Chapter 1 of this study.

The third part of the questionnaire contained statements on a scale of 1–5, similar to the second part, designed to be answered and elicit responses from the participants. It finds that the set of questions focused on the election campaign strategy of a political candidate.

Finally, with the assistance of the statistician, analyze the data using appropriate statistical tools to identify the relationship between factors and strategies associated with voting behavior in the Municipality of Silang, Cavite, and provide possible recommendations. It used descriptive statistics, bivariate statistics, correlation analysis, the chi-square test for independence, and the t-test for independent samples.

Ethical Considerations

Given the importance of ethics in conducting research, the author ensures to respect the rights of the participants, especially going to great lengths to protect their dignity, privacy, and safety. The author guaranteed the confidentiality of the information that the participants gave through the self-made questionnaire, conducted via a Google Form. Also, the participants were given adequate information and reassurance regarding their participation in the study.

The purpose and objectives of this study were explained to the participants, and they were assured that there were no personal or sensitive issues and that they were not forced to answer all the questions that had been covered in the research instrument. Also, they ask the participants' permission to use the information that was obtained from the research instrument.

Moreover, as mentioned earlier, to reassure the participants that their participation in the research is voluntary and will comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, all participants signed a consent form. The letters aim to reassure participants that they willingly participated in the study.

Furthermore, participants were not harmed or abused, both physically and psychologically, during the course of the research. Full consent was obtained from the participants before the study, and any type of misleading information, as well as the representation of data findings in a biased way, were avoided. All information from the participants is for research purposes only.

In contrast, all information is kept secure and confidential by the author, and only authorized personnel shall have access to it. This is guided by and in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The act includes the right to object to the processing of your data, the right to access your data, the right to correct inaccurate data, and the right to erasure or blocking of data.

RESULTS

This chapter presented the results of data gathered from 64 barangays in Silang, Cavite, with 7 participants per barangay, for a total of 448 residents in Silang, Cavite. The findings of the study are discussed in accordance with the order of presentation of the specific problems.

Research Question No. 1. What is the demographic profile of the participants in terms of the following categories:

Table 1. Age of the participants

Age	Frequency	Percentage
30-34 years old	81	18.1
35-39 years old	50	11.2
40-44 years old	64	14.3
45-49 years old	105	23.4
50-54 years old	148	33.0
Total	448	100.0

In Table 1, it showed that most of the participants were aged 50–54 years old, attained with 33% and a frequency of 148 participants. Followed by age ranging from 45–

49 years old with 23.4% and a frequency of 105, 30-35 years old with 18.1% and a frequency of 81 participants, 40–44 with 14.3% and a frequency of 64 participants, and 35–39 years old with 11.2% and a frequency of 50 participants.

Table 2. Sex of the participants

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	194	43.3
Female	217	48.4
Prefer not to say	37	8.3
Total	448	100.0

In Table 2, it showed that most of the participants were female, with 48.4% and a frequency of 217 participants. Followed by males with 43.3% and a frequency of 194 participants. Lastly, they prefer not to say that with 8.3% and a frequency of 37 participants.

Table 3. Years of Residency in Silang, Cavite

Years of Residency	Frequency	Percentage
10-14 years	24	5.3
15-19 years	33	7.4
20-24 years	20-24 years	11.6
25 and up	339	75.7
Total	448	100.0

In Table 3, it showed that most of the participants lived in Silang. Cavite is 25 and up, with 75.7% and a frequency of 339 participants. Followed by 20–24 years with 11.6% and a frequency of 52 participants, 15–19 years with 7.4% and a frequency of 33 participants, and lastly, 10–14 years with a lease percentage of 5.3% and a frequency of 24 participants.

Table 4. Years in being Registered Voter in Silang, Cavite

Years in being Registered Voter	Frequency	Percentage
10-14 years	81	18.1
15-19 years	69	15.4
20-24 years	86	19.2
25 and up	212	47.3
Total	448	100.0

In table 4, it showed that most of the participants had been registered voters in Silang, Cavite, for 25 or more years, which has the highest percentage attained with 47.3% and a frequency of 212 participants. Followed by 20–24 years with 19.2% and a

frequency of 86 participants, 10–14 years with 18.1% and a frequency of 81 participants, and 15–19 years with the lowest percentage of 15.4% and a frequency of 69 participants.

Research Question No. 2. What are factors affecting the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:

When discussing the results, each statement is expected to provide the mean, standard deviation, mode, and interpretation to determine the factors affecting the participants' voting behavior.

Legend:

- 1.0 – 1.79 (Highly Not Agree)
- 1.8 – 2.59 (Somewhat Not Agree)
- 2.6 – 3.39 (Neutral)
- 3.4 – 4.19 (Somewhat Agree)
- 4.2 – 5.00 (Highly Agree)

FACTORS AFFECTING THE VOTING BEHAVIOR

Educational Background

Table 5. Measures of Central Tendency for Educational Background

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate finished his/her bachelor's degree or studies.	4.40	1.035	5	Highly Agree
2. The candidate should finish his/her degree with honor/award or recognition.	3.93	1.08	4	Somewhat Agree
3. The candidate should finish a degree/course related to politics.	3.99	1.059	4	Somewhat Agree
4. The candidate should have at least experiences in leading an organization when he/she is studying.	4.11	0.99	4	Highly Agree
5. The candidate did not study or finish any degree/course.	2.03	1.21	1	Somewhat Not Agree
6. The candidate did not receive any awards or recognition.	2.16	1.181	1	Somewhat Not Agree
7. The candidate did not finish his/her degree/course in a well-known university or college.	2.21	1.205	1	Somewhat Not Agree

8. The candidate has no experiences in leading an organization.	2.08	1.23	1	Somewhat Not Agree
9. The candidate is smart and talented.	4.00	1.088	4	Somewhat Agree

In Table 5, it was discovered that most of the statements have means less than 4.00, with Statement 5 having the lowest mean at 2.03, which means the participants somewhat disagree that the candidate should have at least experience leading an organization when he or she is studying, and Statement 1 having the highest mean at 4.40, which means most of the participants highly agree that the candidate finished his or her bachelor's degree or studies..

Family Affiliation

Table 6. Measures of Central Tendency for Family Affiliation

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate came from a well-known family in their place.	3.65	1.36	5	Somewhat Agree
2. The candidate came from an influential and wealthy family.	3.45	1.35	4	Somewhat Agree
3. The candidate has the same surname of mine or my family relatives.	2.52	1.478	1	Somewhat Not Agree
4. The candidate has the same family orientation, family values and traditional beliefs as my family.	4.02	1.094	4	Somewhat Agree
5. The candidate have a good family image in our barangay.	4.34	0.896	5	Highly Agree
6. The candidate is well-known son, daughter or has a family relative to the former public official.	3.56	1.281	4	Somewhat Agree
7. The family of the candidate has been long in the office and proven in service.	4.01	1.139	5	Somewhat Agree
8. The candidate came from family who made a great contribution in building our place.	4.15	1.025	5	Somewhat Agree
9. The family of the candidate is nice and easy to approach.	4.30	0.905	5	Highly Agree

10. I have indebtedness to the family of the candidate.	2.47	1.481	1	Somewhat Not Agree
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In table 6, it was discovered that most of the statements have means less than 4.00, with Statement 10 having the lowest mean at 2.47, which means the participants somewhat disagreed that they have indebtedness to the family of the candidate, and Statement 5 having the highest mean at 4.34, which means most of the participants highly agreed that the candidate has a good family image in our barangay.

Political Party or Affiliation

Table 7. Measures of Central Tendency for Political Party or Affiliation

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate came from an influential and famed political party	3.53	1.303	4	Somewhat Agree
2. The candidate is a member of well-known political party.	3.68	1.252	4	Somewhat Agree
3. The political party of the candidate has the same advocacies and goal as mine.	3.94	1.049	4	Somewhat Agree
4. The political party of the candidate has many members with my relative or same with my surname.	2.89	1.406	4	Neutral
Table 7. (continued)				
5. The fact that the candidate's party was in power.	3.37	1.382	4	Somewhat Agree
6. The candidate doesn't affiliate to any political party or non- partisan.	3.80	1.180	4	Somewhat Agree
7. The political party of the candidate did a great contribution to our place.	3.94	0.984	4	Somewhat Agree
8. The candidate is not a former member of any political party before he/she decided to enter in this current political party.	3.68	1.066	4	Somewhat Agree
9. The political party of the candidate doesn't involve in some issues before.	4.07	0.966	4	Highly Agree

10. The political party of the candidate is consistent to its ideals and aspirations.	4.10	1.009	4	Highly Agree
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In table 7, it was discovered that most of the statements have means less than 4.00, with Statement 4 having the lowest mean at 2.89, which means the participants are neutral that the political party of the candidate has many members with their relatives or the same surname, and Statement 10 having the highest mean at 4.10, which means most of the participants highly agree that the political party of the candidate is consistent with its ideals and aspirations.

Platforms

Table 8. Measures of Central Tendency for Platforms

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate has a powerful platform that will bring change to our place.	4.46	0.905	5	Highly Agree
2. The platform of the candidate focuses on my belief and interest.	4.08	1.056	5	Somewhat Agree
3. The platform of the candidate is feasible and new.	4.25	0.883	5	Highly Agree
4. The platform of the candidate addresses the current issue of our place.	4.30	0.851	5	Highly Agree
5. The platform of the candidate addresses the current needs of our community.	4.35	0.859	5	Highly Agree
6. The platform of the candidate should not focus on his/her vested self-interest but for the general welfare of the people.	4.29	0.963	5	Highly Agree
7. The platform of the candidate should be holistic in all nature, which means it encompasses the physical, moral, spiritual, psychological and mental needs of his/her constituents.	4.38	0.834	5	Highly Agree
8. The platform of the candidate advocates equality and fairness.	4.43	0.786	5	Highly Agree

9. I will choose the candidate whose platform is not contradicting to what he/she saying and showing to us.	4.38	0.834	5	Highly Agree
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Table 8. (continued)

10. I will choose candidate base on his/her platforms rather than his/her affliation.	4.34	0.806	5	Highly Agree
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In Table 8, it was discovered that all of the statements have means greater than 4.00, with Statement 2 having the lowest mean at 4.08, which means the participants somewhat agreed that the platform of the candidate focused on their beliefs and interests, and Statement 1 having the highest mean at 4.46, which means most of the participants highly agreed that the candidate has a powerful platform that will bring change to their place.

Research Question No. 3. What are the election campaign strategies used by a political candidate to affect the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:

When discussing the results, each statement is expected to provide the mean, standard deviation, mode, and interpretation to determine the election campaign strategies used by a political candidate to affect the voting behavior of the participants.

Legend:

- 1.0 – 1.79 (Highly Not Agree)
- 1.8 – 2.59 (Somewhat Not Agree)
- 2.6 – 3.39 (Neutral)
- 3.4 – 4.19 (Somewhat Agree)
- 4.2 – 5.00 (Highly Agree)

CAMPAIGN STRATEGIES

Campaign Jingle

Table 9. Measures of Central Tendency for Campaign Jingle

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate has a good choice of music in his/her	3.85	1.238	5	Somewhat
2. The candidate use lively and trending choice of music.	3.70	1.161	4	Somewhat
3. The candidate use campaign jingle to put his/her goal and platform in the song.	3.80	0.996	4	Somewhat Agree

4. The campaign jingle of the candidate affects my mood and emotion that's why when	3.66	1.093	4	Somewhat Agree
5. The singer in campaign jingle of the candidate has a good and powerful voice.	3.60	1.185	4	Somewhat Agree

In Table 9, it was discovered that all of the statements have means greater than 3.00, with Statement 1 having the lowest mean at 3.85, which means the participants somewhat agreed that the candidate has a good choice of music in his or her campaign jingle, and Statement 5 having the highest mean at 3.60, which means most of the participants somewhat agreed that the singer in the campaign jingle of the candidate has a good and powerful voice.

Social Media Advertisement

Table 10. Measures of Central Tendency for Social Media Advertisement

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate uses social media platform to showcase his/her plans and platform.	4.08	1.042	5	Somewhat Agree
2. The candidate was endorsed by the well-known social media influencers or	2.68	1.337	1	Neutral
3. The candidate was endorsed by the well-known	2.37	1.255	1	Neutral
4. The candidate doesn't have any social media platform or	2.28	1.308	1	Neutral

In Table 10, it was discovered that all of the statements have means less than 3.00, with Statement 4 having the lowest mean at 2.28, which means the participants somewhat disagree that the candidate doesn't have any social media platform or page, and Statement 1 having the highest mean at 4.08, which means most of the participants somewhat agree that the candidate used social media platforms to showcase his or her plans and platform.

Merchandise

Table 11. Measures of Central Tendency for Merchandise

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mode	Interpretation
1. The candidate uses merchandise to promote his/her candidacy.	3.32	1.249	4	Neutral

2. The candidate is giving merchandises like bracelet, cap, t-shirt and others with imprints of his/her name.	3.21	1.346	4	Neutral
3. The candidate is not giving any merchandise for his/her	3.00	1.298	4	Neutral
4. The candidate should not put his/her name to any merchandise he/she will give.	3.06	1.392	4	Neutral

In Table 11, it was discovered that all the statements have means greater than 3.00, with Statement 1 having the highest mean at 3.32, which means the participants are neutral about the candidate giving merchandise, and Statement 3 having the lowest mean at 3.00, which means most of the participants are neutral about the candidate using merchandise to showcase his or her plans and platform.

Research Question No. 4. Is there significant relationships between factors and voting behavior?

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FACTORS AND VOTING BEHAVIOR

Family Affiliation – Educational Background

Table 12. Relationship between family affiliation and educational background

		Educational Background
Family Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	0.451
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 12, the Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and educational background is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.451 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed about the educational background. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Family Affiliation – Platforms

Table 13. Relationship between family affiliation and Platforms

	Platforms	
Family Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	0.448
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 13, the Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and platforms is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.448 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, they also agreed about the platforms. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Political Party – Educational Background

Table 14. Relationship between Political Party and educational background

	Educational Background	
Political Party	Pearson Correlation	0.335
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 14, the Pearson correlation coefficient between political party and educational background is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.335 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about the political party, they also agreed about the educational background. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Political Party – Platforms

Table 15. Relationship between Political Party and Platforms

	Platforms	
Political Party	Pearson Correlation	0.435
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 15, the Pearson correlation coefficient between political parties and platforms is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.435 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about political parties, the more they agreed about the platforms. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Research Question No. 5. Is there significant relationships between election campaign strategies and voting behavior?

ELECTION CAMPAIGN STRATEGIES AND VOTING BEHAVIOR

Family Affiliation – Campaign Jingle

Table 16. Relationship between family affiliation and Campaign Jingle

	Campaign Jingle	
Family Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	0.545
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 16, the Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and the campaign jingle is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.545 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, they also agreed about the campaign jingle. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Family Affiliation – Social Media Advertisements

Table 17. Relationship between family affiliation and Social Media Advertisements

	Social Media Advertisements	
Family Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	0.192
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 17, the Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and social media advertisements is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.192 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, they also agreed about the social media advertisements. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Family Affiliation – Merchandise

Table 18. Relationship between family affiliation and Merchandise

	Merchandise	
Family Affiliation	Pearson Correlation	0.240
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 18, the Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and merchandise is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.240 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, they also agreed about the merchandise. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Political Party – Campaign Jingle

Table 19. Relationship between Political Party and Campaign Jingle

	Campaign Jingle	
Political Party	Pearson Correlation	0.543
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 19, the Pearson correlation coefficient between political party and campaign jingle is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.543 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about the political party, they also agreed about the campaign jingle. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Political Party – Social Media Advertisements

Table 20. Relationship between Political Party and Social Media Advertisements

	Social Media Advertisements	
Political Party	Pearson Correlation	0.138
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 20, the Pearson correlation coefficient between political parties and social media advertisements is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.138 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about the political party, the more they agreed about the social media advertisements. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

Political Party – Merchandise

Table 21. Relationship between Political Party and Merchandise

	Merchandise	
Political Party	Pearson Correlation	0.251
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000

In Table 21, the Pearson correlation coefficient between political party and merchandise is shown. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship at 0.251 between the two variables, meaning that as the participants agreed about the statements about the political party, they also agreed about the merchandise. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

These are the results of the following hypothesis that were set forth in the null form to facilitate significance testing:

H01: The null hypothesis is rejected. As shown to table 9 to 12, the relationship between factors and voting behavior has enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

H02: The null hypothesis is rejected. As shown to table 13 to 18, the relationship between election campaign strategies and voting behavior has enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant.

DISCUSSION

This part presented the overall interpretations of the data gathered from 64 barangays in Silang, Cavite. Using the self-administered questionnaire to answer the statement of the problems, the author presented the interpretations of the data gathered from 448 participants from Silang, Cavite. The 25 barangays in Silang, Cavite, namely Acacia, Adlas, Anahaw 1, Banaba, Batas, Biga 1, Biga 2, Ipil 1, Ipil 2, Kalubkob, Litlit, Lucsuhin, Narra 1, Narra 2, Narra 3, Poblacion Barangay 1, Poblacion Barangay 2, Poblacion Barangay 3, Poblacion Barangay 4, Poblacion Barangay 5, Sabutan, San Vicente 1, San Vicente 2, Tubuan 1, and Yakal with 175 participants collected data in person. While the remaining 39 barangays in Silang, Cavite, namely Anahaw 2, Balite 1, Balite 2, Balubad, Biluso, Bucal, Buho, Bulihan, Cabangaan, Carmen, Hoyo, Hukay, Iba, Inchican, Kaong, Lalaan I, Lalaan II, Lumil, Maguyam, Malabag, Malaking Tatiao, Mataas Na Burol, Munting Ilog, Paligawan, Pasong Langka, PooC 1, PooC 2, Pulong Bunga, Pulong Saging, Puting Kahoy, San Miguel 1, San Miguel 2, Santol, Tartaria, Tibig, Toledo, Tubuan 2, Tubuan 3, and Ulat, with 273 participants, used a Google form.

Demographic Profile of The Participants in Terms Of The Following Categories:

A. Age

Table 1 indicated that 33% were between the ages of 50 and 54, which represents the majority of the participants. 45–49 years old came in second with a frequency of 105 and a percentage of 23.4%, followed by 30–35 years old with a frequency of 81 and a percentage of 18.1%, 40–44 years old with a frequency of 64 and a percentage of 14.3%, and 35–39 years old with a frequency of 50 and a percentage of 11.2%.

Additionally, in the study of the international IDEA Voter Turnout Website (n.d.), political involvement among young people aged 18–29 is consistently lower than the national norm. Some academics suggest that lowering the voting age might improve these results while also having other positive outcomes. Indeed, defenders of these proposals claim that young voters may offer new and creative ideas to national politics and that people who become politically engaged at a young age will continue to do so as adults.

Many experts, on the other hand, see detrimental side effects of this sort of change, stating that younger voters are more easily influenced and cannot make educated judgments because they do not understand how politics actually works. It is ridiculous to claim that a sixteen-year-old is incapable of having their own viewpoint! Everyone is influenced by fashion, trends, and their peers. This is true for everyone. At sixteen, you are enrolled in a school system that requires you to form arguments and reasoned opinions all of the time in order to advance through the system. If anything, a sixteen-year-old who is constantly required to educate themselves and form opinions is more qualified to do so about state matters than someone who has not needed to do so for years after leaving school. Whether one is for or against minimum voting age legislation, it requires more attention. (Ace Newsletter, n.d.)

Therefore, most of the participants in the study have a basis for their answers, knowing that they've experienced several local elections in Silang, Cavite. That's why the factors and strategies given in the study have several roles.

B. Sex

Table 2 revealed that there were 217 participants overall, with 48.4% of them being women. Males came in second with a frequency of 194 participants and a 43.3% share. They also chose not to say, with a frequency of 37 participants and an 8.3% rate.

In support of the results of the study, according to Encinas-Franco (2021), gender has been shown to have a significant impact on candidate selection in the Philippines. The factor is whether they are the same gender as the candidate. In the electoral process, women have made up 28 percent of the House of Representatives and 29 percent of the Senate since 2019, somewhat higher than the 2020 global average of 25.5 percent. According to global standards, women must attain 30% of the worldwide benchmark to

establish a critical mass in representational politics. When municipal government roles are included, women account for just 23% of all elected seats in the country. However, because many female politicians originate from political families, they have stronger sympathy for their relatives than for women's problems, according to a 2017 study. Several explanations show why women's political engagement is crucial in democracies. Several barriers prohibit Filipino women from entering politics. One of the causes is a dearth of well-developed political parties. There can be no internal party processes controlling women's inclusion in the party slate without party discipline and established regulations inside parties. Traditional standards concerning women's rightful role in the public sphere continue to be an impediment in the Philippines.

C. Years of Residency in Silang Cavite

Table 3 revealed that Silang, Cavite, which had 75.7% of the participants and a frequency of 339, was where most of the participants lived. Then came 15–19 years with 7.4% and a frequency of 33 people, 20–24 years with 11.6% and a frequency of 52 people, and finally 10–14 years with a least percentage of 5.3% and a frequency of 24 people.

The years of residency are considered an important part of choosing a candidate since that is the primary factor that shows that they are aware of who the candidate that they voted for is. Obschonka et al. (2018) provide that in understanding voters' behavior, it explains how and why decisions are made by public decision-makers. To make inferences and predictions about behavior concerning a voting decision, many studies support the idea that residency is one of the factors affected in choosing a candidate aside from gender, race, culture, or religion.

D. Years in being Registered Voter in Silang, Cavite

Table 4 revealed that most participants had been registered voters in Silang, Cavite, for 25 years or more. This was the highest proportion obtained, with 47.3% and 212 participants. 20–24 years came next with a 19.2% frequency and 86 participants, followed by 10–14 years with an 18.1% frequency and 81 participants, and 15–19 years with the lowest frequency and a 15.4% percentage.

Moreover, the Director of the Commission on Elections (COMELEC), James Jimenez, believes that young Filipino voters, who currently account for 52 percent of all registered voters, will make a difference in the national elections on May 9, 2022. The spokesperson confirmed in his presentation that, as of July, 60.46 million Filipinos had already registered for the 2022 general elections, exceeding COMELEC's objective of 59 million. Every age group has their own perception of how they vote after years of voting. Young voters, unlike other voters, are more flexible and prefer to pick candidates while retaining tradition.

Factors affecting the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:

A. Educational Background

The majority of the statements in Table 5 have means that are less than 4.00, with Statement 5 having the lowest mean at 2.03 and the highest mean at 4.40, respectively, indicating that most participants strongly agreed that the candidate had completed his or her bachelor's degree or studies and that the candidate should at least have experience leading an organization while studying. The overall mean for personal stress is 3.21, meaning the participants are generally neutral about the statements under the educational background.

In support of the result, Aman Gupta (n.d.) stated that for any growing nation, education is the most important aspect in all terms, whether it is human development or mechanical development, and that although education comes after hunger, hunger is no longer our major problem after 65 years of independence.

As a result, our politicians must now be qualified and educated. Politicians should have a good level of education since education provides numerous leadership qualities. Leaders who lack knowledge are unable to adapt to change, stifling a country's progress. Education is required for a leader as well as for the country's bright future and prosperity.

B. Family Affiliation

Most of the statements in Table 6 have means that are less than 4.00, with Statement 10 having the lowest mean at 2.47, indicating that participants are somewhat unsure about their debt to the candidate's family, and Statement 5 having the highest mean at 4.34, indicating that participants are generally very certain that the candidate has a positive family reputation in our barangay. The overall mean for personal stress is 3.65, meaning the participants are generally somewhat agreeable about the statements under family affiliation.

As per Ditmars (2017), family is important in shaping voters' political ideology until adulthood, not only in terms of intergenerational transmission but also in terms of the direct effects of family experiences and structure.

C. Political Party or Affiliation

The majority of the statements in table 7 have means that are less than 4.00, with statement 4 having the lowest mean at 2.89, indicating that participants have a neutral opinion about the candidate's political party having many members with their relatives or the same surname, and statement 10 having the highest mean at 4.10, indicating that participants strongly agree that the candidate's political party is consistent with its ideals and aspirations. The overall mean for personal stress is at 3.70, meaning the participants

generally are somewhat agreed about the statements under the political party or affiliation.

Furthermore, electorates identify with a party, and their political affiliations are thought to influence their voting choices (Ranney, 1999). This affiliation stemmed from voters' belief that a certain party might serve their political, economic, and social interests (Green, 2002). Thus, in this scenario, voting preference and behavior are determined by voters' sentiments toward the candidate's political party (Sarlamonov and Jovanoski, 2014). The most relevant indication to voters in terms of which candidate to support is a candidate's party affiliation, even though the current study's findings contradict this assertion; participants regard a candidate's political affiliation as unimportant since they support the candidate, not the party. (Bonneau & Cann, 2013)

D. Platforms

Table 8 shows that all of the statements have means higher than 4.00. Statement 2 has the lowest mean at 4.08, indicating that participants only somewhat agreed that the candidate's platform focused on their beliefs and interests, and Statement 1 has the highest mean at 4.46, indicating that most participants strongly agreed that the candidate has a compelling platform that will bring about change in their community. The overall mean for personal stress is 4.33, meaning the participants generally highly agreed about the statements under the platforms.

In this sense, the platforms of the Constitutional Rights Foundations (n.d.) are important to the election process. They provided candidates with a defined political stance from which to campaign. They gave voters an idea of what the candidates believed in, what issues they believed were significant, and how they intended to solve them if elected.

Election campaign strategies used by a political candidate to affect the voting behavior of the participants in terms of the following criteria:

A. Campaign Jingle

It found that all of the statements in table 9 had means higher than 3.00, with statement 1 having the lowest mean at 3.85, indicating that participants somewhat agreed that the candidate had a good choice of music for his or her campaign jingle, and statement 5 having the highest mean at 3.60, indicating that most participants somewhat agreed that the singer in the candidate's campaign jingle has a good and powerful voice. The overall mean for personal stress is 3.72, meaning the participants generally somewhat agreed about the statements under the campaign jingle.

In addition, a campaign jingle is an effective campaign tool, especially for a politician who is courting an electorate that loves music and a populace that treats singers like gods when they vote for the next big TV singing sensation. As painful as it may be to admit, Filipinos do love to sing and dance, and perhaps they enjoy a bit of entertainment when it comes to actual election campaigns. (Lopez, 1970)

B. Social Media Advertisement

The study found that all the statements in Table 10 had means that were less than 3.00, with Statement 4 having the lowest mean at 2.28 and Statement 1 having the highest mean at 4.08, indicating that most participants were somewhat in agreement with the candidate's use of social media platforms to promote his or her plans and platform, respectively. The overall mean for personal stress is 2.85, meaning the participants are generally neutral about the statements under social media advertisements.

Almost all candidates now have their own websites, and many are active on social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. These sites should include the most thorough list of viewpoints since they are the most direct means of communication with voters looking for information. Given that this is information provided by the candidates, consider the material to be the major "sales pitch" that they will utilize. (League of Women Voters of Newton, n.d.)

C. Merchandise

The study found that all of the statements in Table 11 had means higher than 3.00, with Statement 1 having the highest mean at 3.32 and Statement 3 having the lowest mean at 3.00, indicating that most participants were neutral about the candidate using merchandise to promote his or her plans and platform. The overall mean for personal stress is 3.15, meaning the participants are generally neutral about the statements under merchandise.

When running for office, you need imprinted campaign giveaways to connect with voters. When you hold office, these are good to give out when you can. They build goodwill with their constituents. Supporters want to wear your t-shirts, hats, and buttons. They used water bottles and phone grips imprinted with a politician's name or slogan. It showed their support for the candidate as a brand. They identify with the person and their values. It tells others they are part of a movement or ideal. (Logotech 2021)

Is there significant relationships between factors and voting behavior?

When voters choose between political candidates, they are not just choosing between candidates with different party labels and policy positions; they are also choosing between candidates with different personal backgrounds and characteristics. These personal characteristics ostensibly matter to voters. Voting behavior can be defined as the actions and activities that an individual makes as an autonomous choice, and the decisions he or she makes vary according to different factors and strategies depending on the behavior that influences their political decision. There are many social factors that affect the political attitude and behavior of an individual. The formation of political attitudes and behaviors by individuals has different standards based on what they perceive as a big contributing factor in the election campaign. Theories about choosing a particular party or candidate tend to focus on the individual's decision-making process while trying

to explain and analyze the relationship between every given factor and strategy in the political realm.

Family Affiliation – Educational Background

The Pearson correlation coefficient between family affiliation and educational background is shown in Table 12. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.451, which means that as participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed about the educational background. Table 11 shows that all of the statements' means are higher than 3.00, with Statement 1's mean being the highest at 3.32, which indicates that participants were indifferent about the candidate handing out stuff, and Statement 3's mean being the lowest at 3.00.

Individuals are affected by the context in which they grow up, where the family is expected to play a central role. A person's political participation and engagement are likely to increase if he or she has a parent who has been nominated for political office. The impact is likely to be twofold: an individual whose father or mother is a politician for a given party is more likely to be politically active in general (Aggebor, 2020). Moreover, despite family disagreements and generational gaps, children tend to grow up and vote the way their parents do. Families are generally the first, and often the most enduring, influence on young people's developing political opinions. As people grow older, other influences crisscross the family, and naturally, their attitudes tend to diverge from those of their parents. However, the influence still remains. Logically, the more politically active your family is, the more likely you are to hold the same beliefs. This relationship is less strong on specific issues like school prayer, abortion, and welfare programs, but they all hold the same general political views.

With these, we could set the idea that the family affiliation of a candidate matters to the voters, as does their educational background, whether they finish or not their degree. However, having an educational background is a good factor, but it's not too big a deal for the voters in Silang, Cavite. On the other hand, according to the study Educational Attainment and Social Norms of Voting by Eric R. Hansen and Andrew Tyner (2019), individuals who have attained more education are more likely to view voting as a civic duty. Whether caused by schooling, family background, personality traits, adult social networks, or a combination of these factors, the internalization of voting norms is likely to be more pronounced among people with higher levels of educational attainment. If education instills and reinforces a personal norm of voting, we should find that higher levels of education predict greater agreement that voting is mainly a duty. The prevalence of believing that voting is a civic duty across levels of education is no thought at all since it is defined as the responsibility of a citizen. Of course, the personal characteristics of individuals with and without advanced degrees differ quite a bit. Although having credentials and a good educational background is quite advantageous to the opposition party, based on the results of the survey, we can conclude that having a good educational background is one contributing factor when choosing a political candidate. On the other

hand, this is not totally the basis for choosing a candidate, though in this sense, educational background and family affiliation have a relationship in terms of influencing the behavior of the voters.

Family Affiliation – Platforms

Table 13 shows the Pearson correlation between platforms and family affinity. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, it can be concluded that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.448, which means that the more participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed about the platforms.

Since family affiliation is a contributing factor for a voter to choose a candidate because of the family to which the candidate belongs, regardless of whether this family is from a big clan, a political dynasty, or even a well-known family name, A platform, party program, or party manifesto is a formal set of principles that are supported by a political party or individual candidate in order to appeal to the general public, with the ultimate purpose of garnering the general public's support and votes on complicated topics or issues. A component of a political platform is often called a "plank"—the opinions and viewpoints about an individual topic as held by a party, person, or organization (Manifesto, 2012). Therefore, the platform of a candidate should reflect the principles held by the candidate's family and not contradict their beliefs. Family affiliation and platform should go hand in hand.

Political Party – Educational Background

Table 14 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient for the relationship between political party and educational background. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.335, meaning that the more participants agreed about the statements about the political party, the more they agreed about the educational background.

Party identification, or political party identification, is an important attitude that influences the vote. Most voters identify with one of the two major political parties, and these basic partisan loyalties influence the vote. Party identification is normally measured by asking individuals whether they consider themselves choosing dependent or independent candidates. The direct influence of party identification on the vote occurs in presidential elections. But the indirect influence of party identification is great; partisan loyalties influence evaluations of candidates, assessments of government performance, and perceptions of political events. Put simply, party identification is a perceptual screen—a pair of partisan-tinted eyeglasses through which the voter views the political world. Political affiliation may be somewhat less important now than in the past, but it is still a very significant factor in explaining political orientations and behavior (Abramson,

Aldrich, and Rhode, 2003). Even nowadays, we can see and hear lots of people saying "dilawan o pulahan" to a candidate because of the political party to which they belong. That's why choosing a candidate also reflects the tenants of the political party held by the running candidate. Moreover, the study of intergenerational transmission basically calculates the share of all candidates who are affiliated with the same party for which their parent, sibling, or grandparent has previously been nominated. By connecting our empirical analysis to the underlying theoretical mechanisms, it contributes to the literature on political socialization. We highlight two main theoretical mechanisms, which we have chosen to denote as the socialization pathway and the materialistic pathway. The notion that an individual is socialized into a certain political affiliation reflects the premise that discussions at home are the main transmission mechanism. The materialistic view, on the other hand, is more connected to a rational-choice and political-economy approach to politics, where individuals are seen as utility-maximizers whose demands depend on their material standard, which in turn may be intergenerationally transmitted (Aggeborn & Nyman, 2020). Therefore, having a great educational background is good and can affect our political affiliation because of the trust and assurance they can promise the people.

Political Party – Platforms

The Pearson correlation between political parties and platforms is shown in Table 15 of the findings. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.435, which means that as participants agreed about the statements about political parties, they also agreed about the platforms.

Political parties are key players in Philippine politics. Each national party has a platform-writing committee composed of major party figures and representatives of interest groups closely linked with the party. They do their work in the spring and summer prior to the presidential conventions (Hershey, 2020). In addition, as a result, platform writers have to navigate the tension between candidates' desire for a broad appeal to voters and interest groups' insistence on explicit commitments to their goals. Typically, most of the platform's language involves stirring appeals to the broader electorate. The rest is a laundry list of specific promises to organized groups. Political parties and platforms are vital to a political candidate because the political party will give the candidate help such as machinery, logistics, and financial help during the campaign. On the other hand, platforms are the plans the candidate pursues when he or she is elected president. A political party reflects the platforms upheld by the organization and its principles. Therefore, having a political party will help and provide support for choosing a candidate.

Is there significant relationships between election campaign strategies and voting behavior?

The most intriguing topic about the election is not who won, but why people vote for a candidate regardless of whether that candidate is leading in the poll. Only looking at campaign events and incidents can influence a voter's decision. To establish a complete explanation, the elements of the election must be combined with a more general understanding of electoral behavior. Election campaigns provide candidates and political parties with an exciting opportunity to assess what they truly offer the people of their country and to build their relationships with voters. The better a campaign team or political party plans and prepares for an election, the more votes it will receive and the stronger it will become.

Family Affiliation – Campaign Jingle

Table 16 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient for the relationship between family affiliation and the campaign jingle. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.545, meaning that the more participants agreed with the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed with the campaign jingle.

The campaign should be viewed as a well-organized, purposeful attempt to effect change, and it should be led by careful planning. Successful campaigners study as much as they can about the current situation before taking action. Campaigners used this information to develop a strategy that will help them plan, implement, promote, monitor, improve, and evaluate their campaigns. Regardless of the genre or song, the candidate used the campaign jingle to communicate his or her point of view on why he or she is qualified for a specific post. Family ties are beneficial to a candidate's candidacy because they imply that the candidate comes from a well-known family. As a result, the voter's voting behavior is influenced by the clans or dynasties represented in the campaign jingle.

Family Affiliation – Social Media Advertisements

Table 17 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient for the relationship between family affiliations and social media advertisements. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.192, meaning that the more participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed about the social media advertisements.

We can no longer deny that social media and politics have become inextricably linked. That's because social media plays such an important role in our political dialogue. The modern-day public forum is represented by tweets and comments. The power of

social media to break news in real time has changed the way we consume information (Brent Barnhart, 2021). The candidate used social media channels to promote his or her candidacy and the family to which he or she belongs, making it more significant in the eyes of the public. As a result, having a social media account is easier, more accessible, and free for a candidate because it is open to everybody and requires no payment. The Internet has clearly influenced political campaigns and marketing. Now campaigns have to maintain a digital presence for their candidate, and they have many new channels to distribute messaging as well as communicate with voters.

Family Affiliation – Merchandise

Table 18 shows the Pearson correlation coefficient for the relationship between family affiliations and merchandise. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, it can be concluded that there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis and that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.240, meaning that the more participants agreed about the statements about family affiliation, the more they agreed about the merchandise.

Politicians have traditionally employed strategies to gain popular support. From Roman emperors staging gladiator battles to European kings constructing city improvements, politicians seeking popular approval are nothing new. However, the political game altered when America became a democracy. Voters were able to vote for candidates they preferred. This is where a political marketing approach can help. Marketing, according to Merriam-Webster, is the process of making people aware of a product. The candidate is the product of politics. Presidential campaigns employ a large team of marketing gurus that work to disseminate good messaging across the country. Marketing and politics are inextricably linked. In the article published by Comtix Tickets, "Election Campaign Marketing Strategies to Help You Win," they said that the political candidate should be visible everywhere through online, digital, and print marketing to make sure people see you. It's important that people get to know you and your political platform. Include your photo, name, logo, and tagline on website banners, commercials, display ads, and print marketing. Be active on social media, get to know your supporters, and help them get to know you more. Invest in online advertising. Post up election yard signs, political flags, banners, posters, bumper stickers, and more in all your target neighborhoods! The idea is to help your audience remember you and what you stand for. In this picture, people will see you and your affiliation, whether from your political party or from your family. This branding helps the voters determine if the candidate has a clear vision.

Political Party – Campaign Jingle

The Pearson correlation between a political party's jingle and its membership is shown in Table 19. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship between

the two variables at 0.543, meaning that the more participants agreed about the statements about the political party, the more they agreed about the campaign jingle.

During campaign season, there is one kind of soundtrack that always goes around our streets and highways. These jingles usually offer promises to us like ending corruption, helping the poor, and bringing a brighter tomorrow to the people. And based on the article published by 10 Years of Bandwagon, the effective campaign jingle for the candidate and his political party has to be catchy, not too wordy, and have a lot of repetitions of the candidate's name. The catchiness of the song must be applied to the jingle to make it long-lasting in the heads and minds of the voters. Also, the song should be easy to sing and not too wordy so that we can reduce the amount of information in the song. Lastly, it should be clear and understandable; the memorization of the name of the candidate should be the main goal of the campaign jingle. Furthermore, the song must embody the political party's mission and vision. The song must not separate from the ideals and principles upheld by the party.

Political Party – Social Media Advertisements

The Pearson correlation between political party advertisements on social media and table 20 is shown. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is drawn that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.138, meaning that the more participants agreed about the statements about the political party, the more they agreed about the social media advertisements.

The impact of political context on a political party's organizing and mobilizing strategies has been noted in the literature. Opposition political parties operating in autocratic contexts look for different ways in which they can communicate, organize, and mobilize their members. Advances in digital technology and, in particular, social media have created spaces in which political parties can communicate and mobilize their members (Kwayu, 2021). Political advertising is a form of campaigning that allows candidates to directly convey their message to voters and influence the political debate. By running ads on various types of media, candidates can reach audiences that otherwise may not have been paying attention to the election and build name recognition, highlight important issues, and call attention to the shortcomings of their opponents. On the other hand, we could say that a political party plays a vital role in a candidate's candidacy. Through social media, we can remember how "dilawan and pulahan" affect the voting behavior of every Filipino. That's why it is a tool for the voters to find out if the party has a good standing in their eyes or if the party has made a great contribution to our country. Because of the information age, everything is easy to access, which is why social media platforms play a big role in shaping the image of a candidate's political party.

Political Party – Merchandise

Table 21 shows the political party and merchandise Pearson correlation coefficients. Since the P-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance at 0.01, there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the relationship is highly significant. The conclusion is that there is a positive relationship between the two variables at 0.251, which means that the more participants agreed with statements about the political party, the more they agreed with statements about the merchandise.

A political party is an organization that coordinates candidates to compete in a particular country's elections. It is common for the members of a party to hold similar ideas about politics, and parties may promote specific ideological or policy goals. However, political parties in any political system typically find themselves in a complex and uncertain environment. Change is a constant within all parties and party organizations and in their external surroundings (Van den Berg, 2019). Even though the political party is not totally a contributing factor to the voting behavior of a voter, it can affect the image of the candidate through their political party. During the campaign, the political party is not separated from the merchandise that the candidate is giving to the voters. Basically, the political party of a candidate is the frontline in the campaign for their candidacy because having the endorsement of a political party gives the candidate the confidence to push through the election. That's why putting the name of the party and the name of the candidate on any merchandise is a good idea because they promote the party at the same time.

Conclusions

This study asserted that most participants from the 64 barangays in Silang, Cavite, believed that having an educational background was not enough to be the basis for choosing a public official. Based on our 1987 Philippine Constitution and Omnibus Election Code, there is no such thing as an educational requirement for a candidate to be elected. The Constitution lays down some requisites for an aspiring official to be elected, and one of them is "being able to read and write". So, a political candidate does not need to finish his or her degree before entering politics.

Therefore, the author concluded that, based on these facts, for the selected registered voters in barangays of Silang, Cavite, one of the contributing factors is the importance of having a good and clear platform for a political candidate over his or her achievements in education, family affiliation, and political party. Also, its use of the campaign jingle is a good campaign strategy in the minds of the participants. Having a good and powerful voice, regardless of the genre of the song, is one contributing factor that will affect the voting behavior of a registered voter. Unfortunately, the use of social media platforms and merchandise to showcase the candidacy of a candidate is somewhat less relevant to the participants. Furthermore, the author also concluded that years of residency and years of being a registered voter are most likely to affect the voting behavior of the participants.

Recommendations

The study has contributed to understanding the factors and strategies affecting the voting behavior of registered voters in Silang, Cavite. As the study progressed in Silang, Cavite, it was the chosen area in this study.

The author has observed several recommendations that they would like to address. Here are the following:

First, the author recommended that the other demographic profiles of the participants, such as educational attainment, religion, and language spoken, be considered as predictors of the choice of preferences.

Second, for future researchers, it is highly recommended that they study other preferred age brackets, other years of residency, and other years of being registered voters for the participants.

Third, we recommended conducting the study in other municipalities and cities in the province of Cavite to widen the scope of the study and sum up the overall factors and strategies affecting the voting behavior of other areas in Cavite.

Fourth, it recommended increasing the number of participants in the survey by the respective municipalities and cities.

Fifth, we recommended administering another set of questionnaires that would be able to measure and identify the factors and strategies affecting the voting behavior of the participants in the study.

Sixth, it is also recommended that when gathering data, ask for the assistance of the barangay official per barangay to ensure the reliability of each participant who is qualified for the study.

Seventh, it is suggested that political candidates in Silang, Cavite, used this study as a basis for evaluating their constituents' voting behavior.

Lastly, the author believed that the result of this study should act as a basis for the Commission on Elections, political candidates, political groups, and parties to understand the voting behavior of the registered voters in Silang, Cavite, under the given criteria.

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